

A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW OF CHALLENGES IN URBAN LOGISTICS

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INTRODUCTION

The urban population is expected to continuously grow by annually by 1.84% (World Health., 2016). Consequently, logistics providers will have to provide quality and reliability of services in areas with high congestion. The main objective of urban logistics is to optimize and organize logistics processes and transportation activities taking different factors into account (Benjelloun & Crainic., 2008). So far, analysis of urban logistics problems has rather focused on managerial, engineering techniques or technical aspects than on activities and interaction between the stakeholders. However, the interactions between stakeholders is key for increasing the efficiency with in complex systems (Rose et al., 2016; Stathopoulos et al., 2012; Österle et al., 2015). Therefore, this article presents the analysis of a systematic literature review focusing on challenges related to collaboration among the stakeholders in urban logistics. The paper consists of four sections, starting with the introduction, followed by the research methodology, before the results are presented and discussed, and ending with conclusion.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The systematic literature review was carried out according to Pickering (2013). It is designed to collect, classify and identify challenges in urban logistics related to stakeholders' interaction and engagement. In-line with Pickering (2013) a review protocol was established before we identified selection criteria, collected and analysed the data. It is followed by a results synthesis, and an evaluation. The main aspects covered in the analysis is on private and public stakeholders, collaborative urban logistics and collaborative technology.

Keywords and database selection

We used the online databases available at the University of Bremen, comprising Scopus, Web of Science and IEEE and searched for papers from 2007-2017 (present). The main keywords in the first search were 'urban logistics' or 'city logistics' leading to over 1400 hits. Therefore, additional keywords were iteratively added (1. "challenge", 2."management" and "technical involvement",3. "management" and "business" and "economic" "engineering" and "computer" and "environment", and 4. "stakeholder") till we had three major terms used as filtered criteria. There are "urban logistics with challenges", "management and technical challenges in urban logistics" and "stakeholders in urban logistics".

Selection Criteria

Since each database defines the subjects slightly differently, we roughly classified the papers in the categories 'technical involvement' and 'management' and applied the following keywords: "management", "business", "economic", "engineering", "computer" and "environment".

RESULTS

Table 1 shows how many articles identified in each database with the main search terms. 1,425 papers referred to urban logistics and challenges, so further reduction was necessary. We applied the selection criteria mentioned above leading to a reduction of 53 papers.

Table 1 The number of papers obtained in relevant to challenges in urban logistics

Database	Main keywords	With "challenge"	With 'Management challenges' and 'Technical challenges'	With "stakeholder"
Scopus	587 2007(16)/2016(107) /2017(8)	174	116	25 2011 (1)/2016 (8)
Web of Science	526 2007(6)/2016 (140) /2017(0)	188	132	12 2009 (1)/2016 (3)
IEEE	312 2007(3)/2016(51) /2017(3)	120	25	16 2011 (3)/2016 (2)

Of the 53 identified papers, 3 of them were replicates, so 50 papers are considered and reviewed (see Table1).

There are not so many on challenges in urban logistics involving stakeholders. These papers are mostly related to planning and policy of collaboration between public and private stakeholders or on models and algorithms related to design and support of stakeholders to pursue the collaborative actions. Most of the papers discussing mathematical models and algorithms were excluded as there are irrelevant. Out of relevant 50 papers, 25 papers regarding to the management aspects whereas 25 involving technic challenges.

Management challenges related to urban logistics stakeholders

Of the identified 25 papers, there are 6 review papers referring to design and evaluation of policy and planning in urban logistics, 7 papers relating to the simulation of urban logistics models, and the other 12 papers being for urban studies that proposed policy and planning developments. In the research in aspects of management and urban studies, interactions between stakeholders affect the logistics planning. The interaction of stakeholders in urban areas distribution affect the activities in urban systems in two ways: first related to structure and policy sensitives (strategy and planning) and secondly, related to how operators respond to policy innovation (Stathopoulos et al., 2012). Furthermore, regarding freight and logistics topics, the identified studies had a broad scope looking at social, environmental and economic impacts. For interaction between stakeholders in freight operation, it can be stated that early involvement already in the planning of a system (urban space) is essential for the success (Österle et al., 2015). Insufficient interaction between city authorities and private sectors are for example representatives from industries misunderstanding the municipal planning processes (Eidhammer et al., 2016). There are works in analysis of planning and finding methodology (Graham et al., 2015)

Technical challenges related to urban logistics stakeholders

The proposed keywords resulted in 4 papers related to mathematics and algorithms, 6 papers on information technology systems (IT systems) and 14 papers that consider the challenges in simulation scenario of interaction between multi-stakeholders in urban logistics and evaluation the proposed policy. Those were with technological knowledge, such as using mathematics, algorithm, and IT system to apply for optimizing urban logistics schemes, in combining governmental policies and company initiatives.

For the papers on IT systems, recent investigation involved cognitive management framework for Internet of Things (IoT) and how the use of the technology will lead to intelligent and autonomous applications. Many of the papers visualise the effects using simulation models. Furthermore, several papers discuss how IT systems, algorithm and mathematical models can support the decision making process of the stakeholders involved in warehouse distribution, freight flows, routing task, vehicle loading, size and type of vehicles that could enter urban areas, and possible for congestion charges (Cagliano et al., 2014), which again will benefit public stakeholders (van Heeswijk et al., 2016). Collaborative processes and coordination in managerial organizations are supported by IT systems. Algorithm with vehicle routing problem (VRP) showed that the safety stock and the variance of demand influencing total distribution costs and process reliability (Roeder et al., 2016). Another use of VRP refers to optimize possible setting for urban logistics service of a mid-sized town by applying a number of scenarios (Boschetti & Maniezzo., 2015). Agent-based simulation framework provide possibility setting for city logistics service of a town of about 100,000 inhabitants by assessing interaction between five type of autonomous agent (receivers, shippers, carriers, the Urban Consolidation Center operator, and the administrator) (van Heeswijk et al., 2016). The development of City Logistics concepts and related behavioural issues can be made (van Heeswijk et al., 2016). Especially simulations (through agent-based models) have contributed to research concerning the evaluation of stakeholder behaviour and the interaction of different public and private actors concerning different urban logistics and transport measures.

Discussion

The literature review carried out indicates that the investigation for public stakeholders' interest is different from that of private stakeholders, which leads to a mismatching of the policy making process and the operational processes. For public stakeholders, the identified topics concerns management tools increasing the sustainability which also corresponds to what we have identified in the technical papers, describing the algorithms and models behind used for policy planning and assessment. For private stakeholders, the papers are mainly dealing with involvement in the planning process, i.e. interaction with public stakeholders, but from a micro economic perspective. The technical papers where mostly related to simulation of this interaction or for evaluation of different possible logistics solutions. This review indicates that a holistic approach involving all stakeholders in a system in all phases of a systems life cycle is required, but still difficult to achieve and that there is a need for tools that support effective collaboration between public and private stakeholders. However, to improve the involvement of all stakeholders to in policy development and strategic planning processes tools and approaches are available, but the often not implemented due to a lack of understanding of the necessity of stakeholder involvement in all phases.

CONCLUSION

The literature review shows that there are some works related to managerial issues of public- private interactions for planning urban systems. For the challenges related to technical systems used, we see however that there is little research related to the interaction of private and public systems, which in our view is required in order to improve urban logistics solutions on long term (i.e. either we find papers on traffic management from a public perspective, or we find papers concerning routing optimising from a company perspective, but none on how traffic management systems interact with the route optimisation system etc.). In addition, the focus for private stakeholders is on time and costs, whereas those for public are on sustainability and quality of life for the citizen. Moreover, there have been attempts to investigate how private and public stakeholders should collaborate with each other effectively. There are works looking at how collaboration can be supported. Here we have seen several works on simulation, gamification and participatory design approaches. However, also here the deployment rate seems to be low. We will therefore in the next step focus on the interaction of different IT systems and how

to increase the awareness of the necessity of collaboration and stakeholder involvement in all phases.

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